

June 30, 2021

Natural Product Trial to Reduce Herbicide Stress: Zingerone

Author's Details:

Hüseyin BULUT¹, Nalan YILDIRIM DOĞAN²

¹Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University, Vocational School of Health Services, 24100 Erzincan / Turkey
²Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University, Department of Biology, Faculty of Science and Arts, 24100 Erzincan / Turkey

Received Date: 17-Mar-2021

Accepted Date: 26-May-2021

Published Date: 30-June-2021

Abstract

Combating pests that cause more than 50% of annual food production to disappear has become increasingly important. Pesticides used against agricultural pests play an essential role in increasing the yield. However, pesticides lead to various problems such as deterioration of ecological balance, contamination of nutrients, and increase of environmental pollution depending on the frequency of use. These substances, which have a genotoxic effect, can irreversibly change the structure or gene expression of DNA. Different plant extracts have been using in different organisms to determine the protective effects of natural antioxidants to reduce or prevent the effect of toxins. In our study, the protective effect of zingerone against the genotoxic effect caused by the 2,4-D isooctylester herbicide was investigated in Sönmez-2001, Köprü and Altay-2000 wheat types. For this, IRAP (Inter Retrotransposon Amplified Polymorphism) were performing. It was determined that the dose of 2,4-D isooctylester herbicide increased the retrotransposon mobility with the effect of stress in wheat types, the polymorphism rate resulting from this mobility was directly proportional to the applied 2,4-D herbicide dose, and the GTS (Genomic Template Stability) value was inversely proportional to the dose. It has been determined that the added zingerone causes a decrease in the polymorphism value. Our study results have revealed that 2,4-D isooctylester herbicide causes the least stress in Sönmez-2001 and the most in Altay-2000 type. From the data obtained from our study, it has been determined that zingerone has a protective effect against herbicide stress.

Keywords: 2,4-D Isooctylester, Genotoxic effect, Herbicides, IRAP, *Triticum aestivum*, Zingerone

Introduction

Anthropogenic activities may play an important role in the disruption of the world ecological balance. For instance, the size of agricultural land sown in our country for the last 10 years has decreased from 39.122 thousand hectares to 37.817 thousand hectares. On the other hand, in the same period, the populations of Turkey increased from 71 million to 82 million has been observe (TSI, 2019). The change in agriculture areas in recent years in our country given in Figure 1.

June 30, 2021

Figure 1. Total and per capita agricultural area

With the effect of these factors, it is necessary to obtain more products from more areas (Cheng et al., 2017; Malarkodi et al., 2017; Moreno-González et al., 2017; Rastogi et al., 2017). Diseases, insects, and undesired plants have an important share in the yield loss of plants. The most significant share in the fight against loss of efficiency is the fight against chemical drugs. The total amount of pesticide usage in Turkey rose to 54.098 tons in 2017, with an increase of 8.08% compared to 2016. Fungicides consisted 44% of the total pesticide use in 2017. This is followed by insecticides with 22.8%, herbicides with 23.5%, acaricides with 4.9%, rodenticides with 0.5% and others with 12.4% (EUM, 2019). In recent years, the use of pesticides has been gradually increasing and Erzincan ranks 58th with 46.389 kg/lt in 81 provinces in pesticide use and 44th with 1.046 kg/lt in herbicide use. Types and amounts of pesticides used in Erzincan given in Table 1 (AFM, 2020).

Table 1. The amounts of pesticides used in Erzincan

	Insecticides (kg-lt)	Fungicides (kg-lt)	Herbicides (kg-lt)	Acaricide (kg-lt)	Rodendisit+ Mollusit (kg-lt)	Other (kg-lt)	Total (kg-lt)
Erzincan	2.798	9.297	33.178	1.066	50	0	46.389
<i>Other kg / lt: Plant Activator + Plant Growth Regulator+Insect Attractant+Fumigant+Nematicide</i>							

Depending on the frequency of use of pesticides, residue problems in soil, water and foodstuffs, acute and chronic poisoning, deterioration of ecological balance, adverse effects on non-target organisms, and contamination of nutrients has been observed.

Considering the amount of production and planting area in the world, the most preferred agricultural product group is cereals. Today, approximately half of the cultivated soils are using for cereal production (Köksel et al., 2000). Wheat and wheat products form the basis of carbohydrates taken in daily nutrition and supply most of the daily energy. Complex carbohydrates such as wheat, starch and fiber are among the best and most economical sources. 20% of the protein need of 4.5 billion people in 94 developing countries on the world is meet by wheat products (Brenchley et al., 2012). Turkey is one of the countries that consume most wheat and wheat products in the world. According to the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) statistics, the annual consumption per capita in Turkey is 173.5 kg. In comparison, the annual per capita consumption of wheat products in European Union countries is 102.9 kg. According to 2016 data, cereal production carried out on an area of 11.6 million hectares in our country. While, in 65.3% of this area, wheat were produce, barley was produce in 24.1% and corn in 6.3%. These products has been following by rye (1.2%), paddy (0.9%), oats (0.8%) and triticale (0.3%) production (TSI, 2016).

June 30, 2021

In previous studies of different plant extracts and extracts in different organisms to detect the protective effects of natural antioxidants, reducing or preventing the effect of toxins. For instance, turmeric (Hosseini and Hosseinzadeh, 2018), black cumin (Tavakkoli et al., 2017), milk thistle (Fanoudi et al., 2018), cinnamon (Dorri et al., 2018), barberry (Mohammadzadeh et al., 2018) and ginger (Lee et al., 2018) antioxidant were analyzed.

Ginger features a very rich group with plant diversity and active compounds. Portrait of more than 60 active ingredients in ginger divided into volatile and non-volatile compounds in width. Ginger extracts and properties of gingerol, shagaol, zingerone and zerumbone in vivo and in vitro preclinical models of toxicity of different agents and the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) has been specified in an efficient method (Guahk et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2010; Thongrakard et al., 2014; Kamel et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2018).

	Insecticides (kg-lt)	Fungicides (kg-lt)	Herbicides (kg-lt)	Acaricide (kg-lt)	Rodendisit+ Mollusit (kg-lt)	Other (kg-lt)	Total (kg-lt)
Erzincan	2.798	9.297	33.178	1.066	50	0	46.389
<i>Other kg / lt: Plant Activator + Plant Growth Regulator+Insect Attractant+Fumigant+Nematicide</i>							

In this study, the potential protective role of the ginger extract zingerone against the genotoxic effect of 2,4-D isooctylester herbicide on cultivation the *Triticum aestivum* (Liu et al. 2005), which is one of the model organisms such as *Hordeum vulgare*, *Allium cepa*, *Zea mays*, *Vicia faba* and *Arabidopsis thaliana* used for the detection of genotoxic effect in recent years, has been investigated via Retrotransposon activity.

Materials and Methods

Material

Pure race one-year Köprü, Sönmez-2001, Altay-2000 wheat seeds obtained from NBC Agriculture and Seed Growing (Eskişehir) were sterilized with NaOCl and dried. Seeds of equal size were been placed in petri dishes and germinated with water at 25 °C. The experimental group was formed by adding 2,4-D isooctyl ester in 0.1 ppm, 0.2 ppm, 0.3 ppm, 0.4 ppm and 0.5 ppm doses to the germinated seeds, and 0 ppm, 0.1 ppm, 0.2 ppm and 0.3 ppm zingerone for each dose. 2,4-D isooctyl ester and zingerone were given periodically to the growing seedlings. Seedlings, which were germinated only with water and did not contain 2,4-D isooctyl ester and zingerone, formed the control group. All the samples were been allowed to grow at 25 °C (70% relative humidity).

Germinated Köprü, Sönmez-2001 and Altay-2000 samples were been collected at the end of 14 days according to ISTA (International Seed Testing Association) (2013) seed applications and were kept at -80 °C after being cleaned from external pollution.

DNA Isolation and Determination of Concentrations

DNA were isolated from plant samples for analysis by Inter Retrotransposon Amplified Polymorphism (IRAP) methods. DNA isolation was been performed with minor modifications in the protocol of Shagai-Marooof et al. (1984). Total DNA concentrations were measured by ACTGene Spectrophotometer (ACTGene UVIS-99, NJ, USA) to determine A260 / 280 O.D. Were taken. Based on these results, the total DNA of all samples was been adjusted to 0.5 µg.

IRAP Analysis

Differentiation in the genome from retrotransposon mobility can analysed by IRAP technique. IRAP is a marker system based on mobile elements discovered by Kalendar et al. (1999) to generate DNA fingerprints. It targets a group of retrotransposons containing direct LTRs ranging in size from 100 to 5.000 bp (Kumar, 1999). In this technique, DNA segments between the two LTR sequences are been amplified and the primers are linked to these regions.

PCR was performed with 6 primers in IRAP analyses. The names, sequences and annealing temperatures of the primers used are giving in Table 3.

Table 2. Primers and sequence information used in IRAP analysis

Primer Name	5' → 3' Baz Sequence	T.M.
SUKKULA	GATAGGGTCGCATCTTGGGCGTGAC	63.3 °C
3LTR-5	TGTTTCCCATGCGACGTTCCCAACA	64.6 °C

June 30, 2021

LTR 6150	CTGGTTCGGCCCATGTCTATGTATCCACACATGTA	64.4 °C
NIKITA E2647-5LTR1	ACCCCTCTAGGCGACATCC	58.7 °C
LTR 6149 -5	TTGCTCTAGGGCATATTTTCCAACA	58.4 °C
	CTCGCTCGCCCACTACATCAACCGGTTTATT	65.9 °C

For IRAP PCR, at ratios 2 µl of 10 × PCR buffer, 0.5 µl dNTPs (10 nM), 1.25 µl Magnesium Chloride (25 mM), 1,0 µl primer (5 mM), 1.0 µl Taq DNA polymerase enzyme (5 units) 13.25 µl ultra-pure water, 1.0 µl Genomic DNA was prepared for each sample and primer. The prepared master mix mixtures were placed in a PCR apparatus in PCR tubes with a volume of 500 µl. PCR protocol 95 °C for 2 minutes, 95 °C for 30 seconds 2 cycles, Primer T.M. Temperature 1 minute, 72 °C 2 minutes, 95 °C 30 seconds 41 cycles, 35 °C 1 minute, 72 °C 2 minutes, 72 °C 5 minutes, 4 °C infinite.

IRAP PCR Electrophoresis Protocol

The resulting PCR products were been run on agarose gel. For this, 0.7 g Agarose 10 ml TBE (Tris / Borate / EDTA) pH 8 was been adding and purified to 100 ml with distilled water and heated in a microwave oven and 2 µl Ethidium Bromide was added. Samples were run for 100 minutes at 90 volts ta electrophoresis and visualized with a UV camera.

IRAP Analysis and Determination of Genomic Template Stability (GTS)

For each primer, the presence and absence of amplified DNA bands were determined by negative control IRAP profiles, and the decrease and increase of band intensities were been determined by agarose gel imager and Total LAB TL 120 (Nonlinear Dynamics) software. Genomic mold stability (%) for all primer products;

$$100 \times 1-a / n.$$

In the formula;

a; The IRAP polymorphic profiles determined for each application sample,

n; Was selected as the total number of bands of DNA obtained in the corresponding primer negative control group. According to the polymorphism negative control group observed in the IRAP profiles belonging to the application groups, a new band does not occur or the existing band disappears.

RESULTS

The distribution of the bands that emerged as a result of the IRAP analysis in Köprü, Altay-2000 and Sönmez-2001 wheat types, polymorphism rates and GTS values are given in Table 4, 5 and 6 in detail.

Table 4. Polymorphism rates and GTS values obtained from Sönmez-2001 samples

IRAP	Co	0.	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.	0.5	0.5	0.5
Prim	nt	1	pp	pp	pp	2	pp	pp	pp	3	pp	pp	pp	4	pp	pp	pp	5	pp	pp	pp
Nam	ol	p	m	m	m	p	m	m	m	p	m	m	m	p	m	m	m	pp	m	m	m
e		m	D	D	D	m	D	D	D	m	D	D	D	m	D	D	D	2.	D	D	D
		2.	+	+	+	2.	+	+	+	2.	+	+	+	2.	+	+	+	4-	+	+	+
		4-	0.1	0.2	0.3	4-	0.1	0.2	0.3	4-	0.1	0.2	0.3	4-	0.1	0.2	0.3	D	0.1	0.2	0.3
		D	pp	pp	pp																
			m	m	m		m	m	m		m	m	m		m	m	m		m	m	m
			Zin	Zin	Zin																
			ger	ger	ger																
			one	one	one																
LTR 6149-5	4	7	417			8	847	399	386	1.	1.0	-	699	9	882	878	869	1.	866	842	837
		2				6				1	35	628		3				26			
		8				3				1				6				13			
										2											
										8	873	856	844	6	601	597	586	72	703	688	681
										9				1				2			
										5				2							
														3	337	323	317	52	-	-	-
														4				3	237	237	237
														6							
SLT R1	6	9	905	897	866	1.	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.	1.2	1.1	1.1	1.	1.3	1.2	1.2
		2				0	42	27	11	2	94	67	89	2	53	99	86	32	00	94	87
		6				6				3				6				6			
						8				1				1							
														6	582	576	568	84	831	822	818
														0				4			

June 30, 2021

zingerone application added in addition to 2,4-D herbicide had a positive effect on GTS value in the applications of 0.1 ppm 2,4-D, 0.2 ppm 2,4-D, 0.3 ppm 2,4-D and 0.4 ppm 2,4-D herbicide. However, it was determined that the GTS value did not change in the sample exposed to 0.5 ppm 2,4-D herbicide.

Table 5. Polymorphism rates and GTS values obtained from Köprü samples

IRAP Primer Name	Control	0.1 ppm 2,4-D	0.1 ppm 2,4-D	0.1 ppm 2,4-D	0.1 ppm 2,4-D	0.2 ppm 2,4-D	0.2 ppm 2,4-D	0.2 ppm 2,4-D	0.2 ppm 2,4-D	0.3 ppm 2,4-D	0.3 ppm 2,4-D	0.3 ppm 2,4-D	0.3 ppm 2,4-D	0.4 ppm 2,4-D	0.4 ppm 2,4-D	0.4 ppm 2,4-D	0.4 ppm 2,4-D	0.5 ppm 2,4-D	0.5 ppm 2,4-D	0.5 ppm 2,4-D	
LTR 6149-5	4	1.0	429			1.0	840	419	409	1.0	1.0	-	735	9	813	798	793	1.0	900	856	792
		3				4				6				9				6			
		1				6				0								0			
										9	826	817	811	8	528	513	503	9	711	693	676
										8				5				4			
										3				4				9			
										7				0	409	409	401	7	-	-	-
										0				0				0	348	348	348
										0				0				0			
5LT R1	6	1.2	1.1	1.0	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.3	-	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.1	1.1	856	-	
		13	89	69	03	56	56	03	56	4	93	38	649	3	09	09	94	4	38		470
		6			1			1		1				0				3			
		6			6			6		2				9				6			
										8	700	-	-	8	724	700	700	1.	700	-	-
										6		380	380	0				1		380	390
										0				0				8			
										4								4			
3LTR 5	1
	
		..																			
LTR 6150	4				3	322		3	312	304	-86		3	358	142	140	3	361	356	177	
					4			2					6				6				
					4			2					3				8				
								1	100	98			3	148	-86		3	308	303	296	
								4					6				1				
								4					6				7				
								5					4	441	431	-	6	599	593	587	
								5	314	301	289		4			406	1				
								4					6				2				
								4													
Sukula													3	336				-	-	459	447
													4					5	544		
													4					4			
																		4			
Nikita	6									5	528	-	-	5	543	539	522	5	573	564	563
										3		412	600	4				8			
										6				7				1			
																		4	468	459	-
																		7			388
																		6			
																		1			
Band Numbers	24	2	2	1	1	4	4	3	3	8	8	8	7	1	10	10	9	1	11	11	11
														0				1			
Poly		8.	8.3	4.1	4.1	1	16.	12.	12.	3	33.	33.	29.	4	41.	41.	37.	4	45.	45.	45.
morp		3	3	6	6	6.	66	50	50	3.	33	33	16	1.	66	66	50	5.	83	83	83
hism		3				6				3				6				8			
Rate						6				3				6				3			
GTS		9	91.	95.	95.	8	83.	87.	87.	6	66.	66.	70.	5	58.	58.	62.	5	54.	54.	54.
Valu		1.	67	84	84	3.	34	50	50	6.	67	67	84	8.	34	34	50	4.	17	17	17
e		6				3				6				3				1			
		7				4				4				4				7			

June 30, 2021

A 489 total of bands were formed from 6 primers applied for Altay-2000 type IRAP analysis. It was determined that the size of the bands occurred was between 96 bp and 1.301 bp. Polymorphism values caused by the 2,4-D herbicide in Köprü wheat type varied between 4.34% and 52.17%. The lowest polymorphism was obtained with 4.34% from 0.1 ppm 2,4-D + 0.2 ppm Zingerone and 0.1 ppm 2,4-D + 0.3 ppm Zingerone application. The highest polymorphism was obtained with 45.83% from 0.5 ppm 2,4-D herbicide application. A 12 total of polymorphic bands were obtain from all the primers used in this example. It was determined that 10 of them were band formation.

A reduction in polymorphism was detected at 0.1 ppm 2,4-D, 0.2 ppm 2,4-D, 0.3 ppm 2,4-D and 0.4 ppm 2,4-D doses in ginger extract zingerone applications. In 0.5 ppm 2,4-D herbicide application, there was no change in the amount of polymorphism.

The GTS values of Altay-2000 samples decreased inversely with the 2,4-D herbicide dose applied. GTS values obtained from 2,4-D herbicide applications varied between 95.66% and 47.83%. It was determined that zingerone application added in addition to 2,4-D herbicide had a positive effect on GTS value in the applications of 0.1 ppm 2,4-D, 0.2 ppm 2,4-D, 0.3 ppm 2,4-D and 0.4 ppm 2,4-D herbicide. However, it was determined that the GTS value did not change in the sample exposed to 0.5 ppm 2,4-D herbicide. In Figure 2, the band image obtained from the primer 3LTR5 in Altay-2000 wheat samples is given.

IRAP Primer Name	Control	0.1 ppm 2,4-D	0.1 ppm 2,4-D + 0.1 ppm Zingerone	0.1 ppm 2,4-D + 0.2 ppm Zingerone	0.1 ppm 2,4-D + 0.3 ppm Zingerone	0.2 ppm 2,4-D	0.2 ppm 2,4-D + 0.1 ppm Zingerone	0.2 ppm 2,4-D + 0.2 ppm Zingerone	0.2 ppm 2,4-D + 0.3 ppm Zingerone	0.3 ppm 2,4-D	0.3 ppm 2,4-D + 0.1 ppm Zingerone	0.3 ppm 2,4-D + 0.2 ppm Zingerone	0.3 ppm 2,4-D + 0.3 ppm Zingerone	0.4 ppm 2,4-D	0.4 ppm 2,4-D + 0.1 ppm Zingerone	0.4 ppm 2,4-D + 0.2 ppm Zingerone	0.4 ppm 2,4-D + 0.3 ppm Zingerone	0.5 ppm 2,4-D	0.5 ppm 2,4-D + 0.1 ppm Zingerone	0.5 ppm 2,4-D + 0.2 ppm Zingerone	0.5 ppm 2,4-D + 0.3 ppm Zingerone
LTR 6149-5	8	768	761	756	9	904	899	878	1.	1.0	832	735	1.	1.1	1.0	1.8	1.	1.2	1.1	1.0	
	4				1				0	40			1	11	93	7	2	01	86	68	
	2				3				4				2				1				
									6				4				9				
									5	578	563	556	8	868	859	850	9	711	693	676	
									8				7				4				
									1				2				9				
													5	513	504	496	5	547	-	-	
													2				6	184	184		
													6				3				
5LT R1	6	366	366		1.	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.	1.2	1.1	1.1	1.	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.	1.2	1.2	1.2	
	0				1	10	96	82	2	30	83	77	2	47	38	20	3	89	82	70	
	4				2				3				6				0				
	0				8				9				8				1				
									4	431	-	-	5	519	506	497	5	549	536	-	
									3		262	262	2				5			262	
									6				1				6				
3LTR 5	1	
LTR 6150	4				4	415	406		2	219	211	199	2	277	268	249	3	301	297	288	
					2				2				8				0				
					2				6				1				6				
									1	188	186	181	5	497	490	482	6	603	592	586	
									9				0				1				
									2				2				1				
													1	196	-	-	1	182	176	-	
													9		196	196	8			196	
													9				9				
Sukula	3				7	704	698	656	8	839	830	822	9	909	901	895	6	599	593	587	
					1				4				1				1				
					2				7				6				2				
									5	558	541	532	3	314	310	297	4	423	419	411	
									6				2				2				

June 30, 2021

Figure 4. Changes in the polymorphism-GTS values obtained from the applications of 2,4-D herbicide and zingerone in the examples of Köprü

Figure 5. Changes in the polymorphism-GTS values obtained from the applications of 2,4-D herbicide and zingerone in the examples of Altay-2000

Discussion

The main purpose of agriculture is to obtain the largest possible quantity of high-quality products from the unit area without damaging the ecological balance. Undoubtedly, one of the most important factors limiting this aim is disease, pests and weeds (Topal, 2011). It has been reporting that the loss of crop caused by weeds is about 32%, and this loss reaches nearly half of the damage caused by all plant protection problems (Aydın and Tursun, 2010). The use of herbicides has become an acceptable approach to keep the weeds in agriculture below specific limit values to reduce product losses in order to meet the food needs of the ever-increasing population of the world. However, continuous and high doses of herbicides usage cause environmental pollution and, thus, stress in plants (Bhadoria, 2011).

Pesticides that are frequently using in agriculture are one of the important anthropogenic practices threatening ecological life. 2,4-D is a type of phenoxy acid herbicide (Gehring et al., 1990). They are moderately stable chemicals and cause a slowdown in the development of the products to which they are applied (Donald et al., 1999). Besides, 2,4-D's mutagenic and genotoxic effect depending on its concentration has been stated in various studies (Pavlica et al., 1991; Enan 2009).

Different stresses are known to affect many plant retrotransposons. Retrotransposons, which constitute an essential part of the genome in eukaryotic organisms, are mostly silent and become effective under stress conditions (Jurka et al., 2007). Many studies show that various biotic and abiotic stresses increase the expression of various transcriptional active LTR retrotransposons (Grandbastien et al., 2005; Salazar et al., 2007). In this study, it is aimed to determine the genotoxic effects of 2,4-D isooctyl ester on Sönmez-2001, Köprü, Altay-2000 wheat seeds and to determine whether ginger extract zingerone has a protective effect. Polymorphisms were obtained due to the mobility of retrotransposons in LTR6150, 3LTR-5, NIKITA E2647, LTR 6149-5, 5LTR1, SUKKULA primers used in IRAP analyses. In the highest dose of 2,4-D isooctyl ester herbicide usage, polymorphism values were observed high. It was been understanding that retrotransposons, whose mobility level increased due to the applied herbicide, negatively affected the wheat's (GTS). Changes in the primary attachment points and genome profile due to the mobility of

June 30, 2021

retrotransposons can lead to the formation of new bands or the destruction of an existing band. For this reason, when the samples exposed to herbicide stress and control group samples were comparing, polymorphisms were obtaining. As a result, in our study, it has been determined in IRAP analyses that the stress caused by the 2,4-D isooctyl ester herbicide in cereals induces retrotransposon mobility, and it is understood that the IRAP method can be used to examine the effects of stress factors on retrotransposon mobility.

It is well know that plants respond to environmental cues in a complex and highly coordinated manner at physiological, biochemical and molecular levels (Woodrow et al., 2011, Woodrow et al., 2017). Stress-induced disruption in normal cell functioning requires rapid and broad reprogramming at the molecular level to respond to such adverse conditions (Woodrow et al., 2011, Woodrow et al., 2017; Megha et al., 2018). This reprogramming is based on strict regulation of the expression of stress-sensitive genes, especially at the transcriptional and post-transcriptional levels (Jeknić et al., 2014; Shriram et al., 2016; Khare et al., 2018). The effective resistance of plants depends on the induction of stress-related genes and the synthesis of proteins by their defensive roles (Vinocur and Altman, 2005). Plants have developed complex mechanisms to detect and respond to various abiotic and biotic stresses such as drought, salinity, adverse temperature, heavy metal toxicity and nutrient deficiency (Campo et al., 2012; Zwack and Rashotte, 2015).

In addition, it has been determined that zingerone reduces the stress level caused by the herbicide in wheat samples. The conclusion of our study supports the statement that abiotic stress is a complex progression (Khaksefidi et al., 2015).

It has been determined that the level of stress caused by the herbicide in wheat types is different. Ginger extract zingerone has been founding to play a protective role against the genotoxic effect caused by the herbicide. In addition, it has been determined that Sönmez-2001 type has a higher tolerance to herbicide stress than Altay-2000 and Köprü wheat types.

Suggestions

As determined in our study results, there is a need for herbicides with high selectivity on weeds. Moreover, determining what is effect of stress have occurring in plants on the synthesis of proteins represents an important question mark. Nevertheless, it will be useful to reveal the effect of herbicide applications on plant nominal yield.

Acknowledgment

This study includes FBA-2019-606 projects supported by Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University BAP Coordination Unit. We would like to thank NBC Agriculture and Seed / Eskişehir-Turkey.

Corresponding Author

Hüseyin BULUT-

Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University Vocational School of Health Services, 24100 Erzincan / Turkey

E-mail: huseyinbulut@erzincan.edu.tr

References

- i. *AFM (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry) (2020) <https://www.tarimorman.gov.tr/Konular/Bitkisel-Uretim>*
- ii. *Aydın O And Tursun N (2010) Determination of Allelopathic Effects of Some Plant Originated Essential Oils on Germination and Emergence of Some Weed Seeds. KSU J. Nat. Sci. 13(1):11-17.*
- iii. *Bhadoria BPS (2011) Allelopathy: A Natural Way Towards Weed Management. Ajea 1 (1):7-20.*
- iv. *Brenchley R, Spannagl M, Hall N (2012) Analysis of the bread wheat genome using whole-genome shotgun sequencing. Nature 491:705-710.*

June 30, 2021

- v. Campo MT, Fouad H, Solís-Bravo MM, Sánchez-Uriz MA, Mahillo-Fernández I, Esteban J (2012) Cost-effectiveness of different screening strategies (single or dual) for the diagnosis of tuberculosis infection in healthcare workers, *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiology* 33(12):1226-1234.
- vi. Cheng H, Marín-Sáez J, Romero-González R, Frenich AG (2017) Simultaneous determination of atropine and scopolamine in buckwheat and related products using modified QuEChERS and liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry. *Food Chem.* 218:173-180.
- vii. Donald DB, Syrgiannis J, Hunter F, Weiss G (1999) Agricultural pesticides threaten the ecological integrity of northern prairie wetlands. *Sci. Total Environ.* Jul., 23:173-81.
- viii. Dorri M, Hashemitabar S, Hosseinzadeh H (2018) Cinnamon (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*) as an antidote or a protective agent against natural or chemical toxicities: a review *Drug and chemical toxicology*, 41 (3):338-351.
- ix. Enan MR (2009) Genotoxicity of the herbicide 2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D): higher plants as monitoring systems. *JTFE*, 25:147-155.
- x. EUM (Environment and Urban Ministry) (2019). <https://environmentalindicators.csb.gov.tr/pesticide-use-i-86060>.
- xi. Fanoudi, S. Alavi, M.S. Karimi, G. Hosseinzadeh H. 2018. "Milk thistle (*Silybum Marianum*) as an antidote or a protective agent against natural or chemical toxicities" a review *Drug Chemster. Toxicology*, 1-15.
- xii. Gehring CA, Irving HR, Parish RW (1990) Effects of auxin and abscisic acid on cytosolic calcium and pH in plant cells. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 87:9645-9649.
- xiii. Grandbastien MA, Audeon CE, Bonnivard JM, Casacuberta B, Chalhoub APP, Costa QH, Lea D, Melayah M, Petit C, Poncet SM, Tam MA, Van Sluys C and Mhiria (2005) Stress activation and genomic impact of Tnt1 retrotransposons in Solanaceae. *Cytogenet Genome Res.*, 110: 229- 241.
- xiv. Guahk G-H, Ha SK, Jung H-S, Kang C, Kim C-H, Kim Y-B, Kim SY (2010) Zingiber officinale Protects HaCaT cells and C57BL/6 Mice from Ultraviolet B-Induced Inflammation, *Journal of Medicinal Food* Vol. 13, No. 3.
- xv. Hosseini H and Hosseinzadeh H (2018) Antidotal or protective effects of *Curcuma longa* (turmeric) and its active ingredient, curcumin, against natural and chemical toxicities: a review *Biomed Pharmacother*, 99:411-421.
- xvi. ISTA (International Seed Testing Association) (2013) *International Rules for Seed Testing Edition*, Zurich, Switzerland.
- xvii. Jeknić Z, Pillman KA, Dhillon T, Skinner JS, Veisz O, Cuesta-Marcos A, Hayes PM, Jacobs AK, Chen THH, Stockinger EJ (2014) Hv-CBF2A overexpression in barley accelerates COR gene transcript accumulation and acquisition of freezing tolerance during cold acclimation. *Plant Mol. Biol.*, 84:67-82, 10.1007/s11103-013-0119-z.
- xviii. Jurka J, Kapitonov VV, Kohany O, Jurka MV (2007) Repetitive Sequences in Complex Genomes: Structure and Evolution. *Annu Rev Genomics Hum Genet.* 8:241-59.
- xix. Kalendar, R., Flavell, A.J., Ellis, T.H.N., Sjakste, T., Moisy, C., and Schulman, A.H. (1999) Analysis of plant diversity with retrotransposon-based molecular markers. *Heredity.* 106(4): 520–530.
- xx. Kamel B, Bourguignon L, Marcos M, Ducher M, Goutelle S (2017) Is Trough Concentration of Vancomycin Predictive of the Area Under the Curve? A Clinical Study in Elderly Patients. *Ther Drug Monit.* 39(1):83-87. doi: 10.1097/FTD.0000000000000359.

June 30, 2021

- xxi. Khaksefidi RE, Mirlohi S, Khalaji F, Fakhari Z, Shiran B, Fallahi H, Rafiei F, Budak H, Ebrahimie E (2015) *Differential Expression of Seven Conserved microRNAs in Response to Abiotic Stress and Their Regulatory Network in Helianthus Annuus*. *Front Plant Sci*, 17;6:741. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2015.00741.
- xxii. Khare T, Shriram V, Kumar V (2018) *RNAi technology: the role in development of abiotic stress-tolerant crops*. *Biochemical, Physiological and Molecular Avenues for Combating Abiotic Stress Tolerance in Plants*, Elsevier, 117-133, 10.1016/B978-0-12-813066-7.00008-5.
- xxiii. Kim MK, Chung SW, Kim DH, Kim JM, Lee EK, Kim JY, Ha YM, Kim YH, No JK, Chung HS, Park KY, Rhee SH, Choi JS, Yu BP, Yokozawa T, Kim YJ, Chung HY (2010) *Modulation of age-related NF-kappaB activation by dietary zingerone via MAPK pathway*. *Exp Gerontol*. 45:419–26.
- xxiv. Köksel H, Sivri D, Özboy Ö, Başman A, Karacan H (2000) *Hububat Laboratuvarı El Kitabı*, Ceylan Matbaası, Ankara.
- xxv. Kumar, L.S. (1999) *DNA Markers in Plant Improvement: An Overview*. *Biotechnology Advances*. 17, 143-182.
- xxvi. Lee J, Oh SW, Shin SW, Lee KW, Cho JY, Lee J (2018) *Zingerone protects keratinocyte stem cells from UVB-induced damage*. *Chemico-biological interactions*, 279:27-33.
- xxvii. Liu L, Wang YX, Zhou J, Long F, Sun HW, Liu Y, Chen YZ, Jiang CL (2005) *Rapid non-genomic inhibitory effects of glucocorticoids on human neutrophil degranulation*, *Inflamm Research*, 54(1):37-41.
- xxviii. Malarkodi C, Rajeshkumar S, Annadurai G (2017) *Detection of environmentally hazardous pesticide in fruit and vegetable samples using gold nanoparticles*. *Food Control*, 80:11-18.
- xxix. Megha S, Basu U, Kav NNV (2018) *Regulation of low temperature stress in plants by microRNAs* *Plant Cell Environ.*, 41:1-15, 10.1111/pce.12956.
- xxx. Mohammadzadeh N, Mehri S, Hosseinzadeh H (2017) *Berberis vulgaris and its constituent berberine as antidotes and protective agents against natural or chemical toxicities*, *Iranian journal of basic medical sciences* 20 (5):538-551.
- xxxi. Moreno-González D, Pérez-Ortega P, Gilbert-López B, Molina-Díaz A, García-Reyes JF, Fernández-Alba AR (2017) *Evaluation of nanoflow liquid chromatography high resolution mass spectrometry for pesticide residue analysis in food*. *J. Chromatogr. A*, 1512:78-87.
- xxxii. Pavlica M, Papes D, Nagy B (1991) *2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid causes chromatin and chromosome abnormalities in plant cells and mutation in cultured mammalian cells*. *Mutat Res*. 263:77-81.
- xxxiii. Rastogi L, Dash K, Ballal A (2017) *Selective colorimetric/visual detection of Al³⁺ in ground water using ascorbic acid capped gold nanoparticles*. *Sensor Actuat B-Chem*, 248: 124-132.
- xxxiv. Saghai-Marooif MA, Soliman KM, Jorgensen RA, Allard RW (1984) *Ribosomal DNA spacer-length polymorphism in barley: mendelian inheritance, chromosomal location, and population Dynamics*. *Proceedings of the National Academy Sciences*, 81: 8014-8019.
- xxxv. Salazar M, González E, Casaretto JA, Casacuberta JM, Ruiz-Lara S (2007) *The promoter of the TLC1.1 retrotransposon from Solanum chilense is activated by multiple stress-related signaling molecule*. *Plant Cell Rep.*, 26:1861-1868.
- xxxvi. Shriram V, Kumar V, Devarumath RM, Khare TS, Wani SH (2016) *MicroRNAs as potential targets for abiotic stress tolerance in plants*. *Front. Plant Sci.*, 7:8173389-8173817, 10.3389/fpls.2016.00817

June 30, 2021

- xxxvii. Tavakkoli A, Ahmadi A, Razavi BM, Hosseinzadeh H (2017) Black seed (*Nigella sativa*) and its constituent thymoquinone as an antidote or a protective agent against natural or chemical toxicities Iran, *Iranian journal of pharmaceutical research*, 16:2-23.
- xxxviii. Thongrakard V, Rossella T, Carlo F, (...)Ciro I (2014) Turmeric Toxicity in A431 Epidermoid Cancer Cells Associates with Autophagy Degradation of Anti-apoptotic and Anti-autophagic p53 Mutant, July 2014 *Phytotherapy Research* 28(12) DOI: 10.1002/ptr.5196.
- xxxix. Topal S (2011) Allelokimyasalların herbisit etkileri. *Dumlupınar Üniversitesi, Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 25:1302-3055.
- xl. TSI (Turkish Statistical Institute) (2019) <http://www.tuik.gov.tr/UstMenu.do?Metod=temelist>
- xli. TSI (Turkish Statistical Institute) (2016) <http://www.turkstat.gov.tr/UstMenu.do?metod=temelist>.
- xlii. Vinocur B, Altman A (2005) Recent advances in engineering plant tolerance to abiotic stress: achievements and limitations, *Biotechnology*, 16 (2):123-132.
- xliii. Woodrow P, Ciarmiello LF, Annunziata MG, Pacifico S, Iannuzzi F, Mirto A, D'Amelia L, Dell'Aversana E, Piccolella S, Fuggi A, Carillo P (2017) Durum wheat seedling responses to simultaneous high light and salinity involve a fine reconfiguration of amino acids and carbohydrate metabolism *Physiol. Plant.* 159:290-312, 10.1111/ppl.12513.
- xliv. Woodrow P, Pontecorvo G, Ciarmiello LF, Fuggi A, Carillo P (2011) *Ttd1a* promoter is involved in DNA-protein binding by salt and light stresses. *Mol. Biol. Rep.*, 38:3787-3794, 10.1007/s11033-010-0494-3.
- xlvi. Yang P, Chen Y, Wu H, Fang W, Liang Q, Zheng Y, Olsson S, Zhang D, Zhou J, Wang Z, Zheng W (2018) The 5-oxoprolinase is required for conidiation, sexual reproduction, virulence and deoxynivalenol production of *Fusarium graminearum*. *Curr Genet* 64(1):285-301.
- xlvi. Zwack PJ, Rashotte AM (2015) Interactions between cytokinin signalling and abiotic stress responses, *Journal Explorer Botany*, 66: 4863-4871.